

ENSURING ROAD SAFETY IS THE MOST IMPORTANT ISSUE OF THE CURRENT TIME

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Abstract . In this article, the measures taken in the field of road safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the instructions given by our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev and legal documents are analyzed, and the development trend of road safety is studied. Legislation related to the field is periodized, that is, it is divided into three stages. In the article, during the study of legal documents related to road traffic safety, attention was paid to their quantity and based on the need to systematize them, referring to foreign experience, the legal documents of each field were studied as a unique solution to the problem, and as a result, traffic accidents were prevented. ways have been considered.

Keywords: traffic accident, traffic safety, driver, law, decision, legislation, internal departmental documents, regulation.

Introduction. The high death rate of people, especially young people and children, who die and are injured due to road traffic accidents (hereinafter referred to as accidents) makes the need to ensure road safety one of the most important issues on the agenda. A person's life and health constitute his vital interests, protecting him and ensuring his inviolability is one of the duties of the state.

According to Article 13 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal principles, according to which a person's life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are the highest value [1].

On February 11, 2022, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a video selector meeting was held on measures to ensure human safety on the roads. The leader of our country emphasized that this issue has not been seriously and analytically discussed by any leader or organization in the last five years, the laws and works in this field are completely unsatisfactory, the issue of road safety has gone out of the way, and this is the reason for the objection of many people [2].

In 2021, more than 10,000 traffic accidents occurred in our republic, in which more than 9,000 people were injured. The saddest thing is that about 2,500 people died. According to analysis, 25 percent of road accidents are caused by poor road conditions and poor infrastructure. At the meeting, the areas where traffic accidents occur a lot were pointed out, and disciplinary measures were imposed on the officials.

Educational programs for the training, retraining and upgrading of motor vehicle drivers at the Department of Automotive Training of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. PQ-190 "On measures to reliably ensure human safety on highways and drastically reduce the number of deaths" and the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 31, 2018 " Training and retraining of drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles and drivers of motor vehicles No. 408 on measures to further improve the licensing procedure for the provision of non-state educational services for conducting theoretical and practical exams for obtaining a driver's license and It was developed on the basis of decisions No. 393 of July 20, 2022 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of training, retraining and upgrading the skills of motor vehicle drivers and their examination" [3, 4, 5, 6].

In connection with the submission to the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the development and approval of training programs for the training, retraining and improvement of motor vehicle drivers, the training of drivers in the category "A", "B", "C", "BC" at the Ministry of Internal Affairs, "City electric vehicles" Training programs for driver training, retraining for "C", "D", "BE", "CE", "DE" categories, as well as retraining and professional development of driver-guides and teachers were prepared [12].

As mentioned, most of the traffic accidents are caused by drivers' deliberate disregard for traffic rules and inexperience, and pedestrians' failure to follow the rules. Therefore, it was noted

that this year the national program "Safe Road and Safe Pedestrian" will be implemented in all regions.

Research methodology . The Legislature and authorities were tasked with revising and radically improving the legislation on traffic . Because the cases of gross violations and their repetition have increased.

In order to ensure the inevitability of punishment, from now on, it was decided to introduce a system of penalty points for each offense. For example, if the driver increases the speed, 1 point is counted, if he runs a red light, 3 points are counted. If the total number of violations in one year exceeds 12 points, the driver will be deprived of the right to drive and retake the test.

In addition, the procedure for determining the amount of the insurance premium paid in the case of mandatory liability insurance of drivers will be introduced based on penalty points.

Also, a new type of responsibility called "traffic disorder" will be introduced for driving a car erratically and interfering with other drivers.

The head of state noted that the traffic rules are outdated and issued an order to update them based on international standards, having studied the opinions of experts and drivers.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 4, 2022 "On measures to reliably ensure human safety on highways and drastically reduce the number of deaths" requires training of guides and provision of examination centers with modern equipment [3]. The quality of training of drivers and their culture and psychological state on the roads are of great importance in ensuring traffic safety.

Results of research and discussion. The driver must always control his thoughts to ensure the safety of the traffic. Safety on the road depends not only on the driver, but also on many other factors. Therefore, the driver should never rely on accidental safety, but rather think about the danger and do everything to avoid it. One should never decide on a next move or maneuver unless the situation is completely clear. The smallest mistake of the driver can have very serious consequences. The complexity of the situation, as a rule, arises unexpectedly, and this should be taken into account. Therefore, acting in accordance with the established rule, which allows you to make a reasonable assessment of the situation on the road and makes the driver's mind always alert. The driver should see your activity in anticipation, not prediction.

It is better to think of everyone as blind, deaf and stupid in decision-making than to call everyone good-seeing, hearing and intelligent. This rule helps the driver to exclude in his thoughts the unreasonable expectation of the adequacy of the behavior of another participant in the movement (driver, pedestrian) or an attempt to think for him . A driver who follows this rule will not have an accident. Therefore, the driver must act according to the situation, but independently protect himself from possible mistakes of another driver or pedestrian. The more daily problems and the more complex they are, the higher the activity of the mind, and the lower the driving speed can be. A driver should not let everyday problems occupy his mind and thought processes while driving! The ability to control the driver's emotions is the key to safe driving. We must not forget that the internal state of a person is a powerful factor that determines his reliability. Considering that we live in a situation with a high probability of stressful effects (at work, family, on the street, etc.), it is very important to have methods of self-regulation of one's condition, to ensure traffic safety and to maintain one's health [7, 8, 9].

A short rule of thumb for the correct formation of the road mindset is to make decisions thoughtfully, thoughtfully, and carefully. This is the golden rule for almost all driving situations. Let's see what actions this provision provides [10].

1. Makes you think about road safety when crossing a secondary road intersection.
2. It draws the driver's attention to the vehicle crossing the secondary road.
3. It encourages to be prepared for any unexpected events, which may be related to the inappropriate actions of the driver who deviates from the secondary road, because he may be drunk, sick, etc., he may simply not notice the "Give Way" sign or see the driver, etc.
4. This encourages the driver to be ready to give up the priority established by the traffic rules in relation to the vehicle standing on the secondary road.

"For the driver, I am primary, he is secondary" can end like this: "He is in the roadside ditch, and the driver is in the other world."

If a driver on the main road takes this as a guarantee against an accident, then an accident is guaranteed.

Each driver should have their own personality, and while admiring the actions of individual drivers, one should not allow negligence. This is often observed at intersections, where a novice driver starts with a delay after the green light of the traffic light or waits for a long time for favorable conditions to pass the vehicle at the intersection and turn left. The drivers behind him start honking and rushing him. Of course, there is an exception to this rule, if when it starts to turn, the driver begins to reverse and hears the signals sent to the driver from behind the stopped vehicle. In other cases, you should not respond to signals coming from behind, which may prompt the driver to move suddenly.

Failure to follow the speed limit can often lead to accidents. The driver increases the speed not only due to the operation of unconscious psychological mechanisms, but often due to his conscious misregulation. Each speed regime imposes its own requirements on the professional training and psychophysiological capabilities of the driver, and the higher the speed, the greater the requirements.

When one vehicle is constantly rearranging on the roads, causing inconvenience to all other drivers, such a situation can be observed frequently on other roads as well. The actions of such a driver lead to haste. Rushing causes an accident. Haste is a sign of insufficient professionalism and manifestation of negative mental attitudes. Therefore, if the driver does not want an accident, he should not rush. You should never rush. Do not forget the rule: haste shortens not only time, but also the path to the grave. But, unfortunately, there is no way to go back in time to correct a mistake.

The manifestation of haste is multifaceted. This is breaking the speed limit and starting to move without waiting for the green signal at the yellow traffic light, and moving from the intersection when the red signal changes to a yellow signal, turning in a prohibited place, making a sudden maneuver after accidentally identifying an important place, etc. The driver should know that clear traffic rules and appropriate means of traffic control (traffic lights, signs, lines, etc.) only organize the movement of vehicles, but do not guarantee their safety. Safety is provided by the driver. The driver's safety is in his own hands.

Another type of haste is to make a sudden maneuver at a point of interest that is important to the driver. As a result, a quick reaction to the execution of the maneuver, as a rule, leads to an accident. Thus, if the driver loses his direction on the route, he must stop the car and regain his health. The driver should never try to look for important points of interest on the road while driving to determine their location, especially in dense and intensive traffic. Keeping an optimal distance is the key to safe driving. Keeping distance is not easy, especially for a novice driver. If the driver keeps the intermediate distance as taught by the teacher (the distance to the car in front should be equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ of the car's speed in meters, expressed in km/h, for example, when $v=60$ km/h, the intermediate distance should be $l = 30$ m) traffic accident prevented [11, 12, 13]. If the driver reduces the distance, he will not be able to stop in time during sudden braking in front of the moving vehicle. When maintaining a safe distance, it is important to think about how to maintain a safe distance at all times, not about preventing someone from getting in front of the driver's car at all costs. When placing other vehicles on the road, the driver must be completely calm, regardless of whether he is a beginner or a professional driver. In general, ambition is one of the most insidious enemies of the driver, because it sometimes manifests itself suddenly and with great force, suppresses the mind and causes a negative attitude. Whatever the driver does on the road, his safety is largely determined by his discretion. Caution should precede any action.

Bad perception is the beginning of tragedy. Think + look around + make a decision + warn everyone + perform a control action = safe maneuvering formula [14, 15, 16].

Before slowing down or making a maneuver, do not forget to look in the mirror, and in the second case, turn on the turn signal.

Driver distraction while driving can lead to the most expensive break in life.

Practices show that even a short-term distraction of the driver from driving the car for 1-2 seconds in certain situations can lead to an accident.

When the driver turns on the light signal, it means ensuring his own safety and attracting other drivers.

If the driver decides to make a maneuver, he must attract everyone's attention to ensure safety. This rule guarantees optimal interaction with other drivers and helps reduce tension in traffic. Unfortunately, it is often not implemented due to the lack of culture of drivers. Any other lane change without warning not only annoys the surrounding drivers but also endangers them.

Some drivers do not use their turn signals unless there are other road users nearby. It shows that the driver does not pay attention to his individual actions, but how important it is to form strong reflexes in himself, even in situations that are not under control and there are no other road users.

In preventing the tragedies caused by sun glare, especially in the autumn and spring seasons, the use of ordinary light protection glasses is not always effective, but the use of special tinted glasses can help.

Conclusions. The work carried out by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of road safety ensures the safety of people's lives in our Republic, as well as the reduction of traffic accidents on highways. As a result of ensuring traffic safety on highways, improving driver training schools, improving the qualifications of teachers and driver-guides, and providing driving test centers with modern and innovative equipment, the driver's knowledge will be increased, strong professional skills will be formed, and his culture will increase. As a result, traffic accidents can be prevented and reduced.

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